

Bond Increment Molecular Electrostatic Potentials and Fields for the Theoretical Analysis of Hydrogen-bonded Complexes

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The very rapid semiquantitative bond increment method for the calculation of molecular electrostatic potentials (MEP) and fields (MEF) was applied to study hydrogen-bonded systems. Using MEP of 18-crown-6 an overall classification of binding modes of various guests is possible, while MEP of the complex between β -trypsin and basic pancreatic trypsin inhibitor (BPTI) is used to locate most probable sites of hydration. The conclusions drawn from MEP and MEF of various systems may be useful in forming working hypotheses for experimental studies and more sophisticated theoretical calculations.

SEVERAL types of complicated hydrogen-bonded complexes, like host-guest, protein-ligand and protein-protein associations, are important targets of modern chemical research. Accordingly, calculation of interaction energies and preferred relative orientations in these complexes is a major challenge to theoretical chemistry. Sophisticated molecular mechanics methods¹ yield accurate results but they need powerful minicomputers and depend heavily on parametrisation, thus their use requires considerable experience. In this paper, we describe two applications of a simple method to the analysis of hydrogen-bonded systems. The advantage of our approximation over others is that it can be programmed to microcomputers, like IBM PC XT.

It is known that molecular electrostatic potential maps² (MEP) and fields³ (MEF) can be successfully applied to the qualitative or semiquantitative analysis of hydrogen bonds in molecular complexes or in hydrated species. *Ab initio* quantum chemical calculation of the MEP or MEF needs the molecular wave function which makes such studies prohibitive for larger systems. Earlier, we proposed a method^{4,5} which builds up the wave function from strictly localised and transferable molecular orbitals and results in a simple mathematical expression for the MEP involving computational work which increases with the first (instead of the third or fourth) power of the number of bonds in the molecule. Using analytical derivatives of the necessary integrals, the MEF can also be calculated. In the following, we illustrate the efficiency of our bond increment method on two selected examples.

Binding of guests to 18-crown-6 :

18-Crown-6 (1,4,7,10,13,16-hexacyclooctadecane, Fig. 1) is one of the best known crown ethers and

it serves as an excellent model for host-guest complexation⁶. It binds several types of ligands especially those containing one or more acidic

Fig. 1. Complex of 18-crown-6 with hydrazinium cation. Hydrogen atoms of the host are omitted for clarity. Reference points for negative and positive potential regions are indicated by empty and full circles, respectively. MEP values are in kJ mol^{-1} .

hydrogen atoms (e.g. methylammonium⁷, hydrazonium⁷ and hydroxylammonium⁷ cation, acetonitrile⁸). Diazonium salts where the azo group is positively charged may be also complexed⁹. Earlier it was thought that the binding power depends only on the geometric size of the guest. However, systematic crystallographic studies have shown that hydrogen bonding plays a major role in complexation too⁶.

In the following, we make some predictions concerning the spatial arrangement of various guests in complexes with the D_{3d} conformation of 18-crown-6. We use our electrostatic lock-and-key model¹⁰ which analyses host-guest binding in terms

of complementarity between the electrostatic potential in some reference points around the crown ether and its ligand. Reference points (Fig. 1) are located in possible proton acceptor and donor binding sites at a distance of 100 pm from the parent atom in hypothetical lone-pair and XH-bond directions, respectively. Complementarity between host and guest electrostatic patterns is the better (*i.e.* the interaction is the stronger), the larger is the number of matching reference points (*i.e.* those with potentials of the opposite sign). Additionally, the sum of potential products yields further information on the magnitude of the interaction energy. X-Ray crystallographers use hydrogen bond distances and angles to analyse the interaction but this is not always sufficient, especially, if energetics is also important. Furthermore, in the complex of diazonium salts with 18-crown-6 no hydrogen bond exists and complexation cannot be discussed merely on the basis of bond lengths and bond angles.

The electrostatic pattern of 18-crown-6 is depicted in Fig. 1. The potential is most negative (-592 kJ mol^{-1}) in reference points within the ring. This is the region which is preferred by the complementary positive pattern of various guests, like small monoatomic cations (Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+). In case of larger ligands (Rb^+ , Cs^+ , $\text{R}-\text{NH}_3^+$ and other polyatomic molecules) the close contact with ether oxygen atoms hinders deep penetration and the guest emerges from the ring and may partly interact with the less positive region (-444 kJ mol^{-1}) around the upper and lower reference points. That side of the ligand will face the ring which has a more positive potential around it. So for methylammonium, H_3CNH_3^+ , where the potential in reference points around NH_3^+ and CH_3 is 761 and 524 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively, the ammonium group will face the polyether⁷. On the other hand, in acetonitrile, NCCH_3 , the potentials in reference points near the nitrile and methyl groups are -554 and 110 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively, it is now the methyl group which comes closer to the ring⁸.

Complexes of 18-crown-6 with hydroxylammonium (HONH_3^+) and hydrazinium (H_2NNH_3^+) cations show interesting features⁷. They penetrate deeply

into the host, because their potential patterns may interact with the negative regions above and below the polyether ring (Fig. 1). In these complexes, a four- or five-point matching is possible which clearly increases the interaction energy. The hydrazinium ion is not symmetrically positioned, the tetracoordinated nitrogen is slightly shifted towards the polyether plane. This can be understood in terms of the matching potential patterns. For the reference point in the lone-pair region of the tricoordinated nitrogen atom, the interaction is less attractive, so it is energetically favourable if the NH_3^+ group moves inside the negative potential region of the ring.

For HONH_3^+ two reference points exist around the oxygen atom where the interaction is smaller (potential values being equal by symmetry are 331 kJ mol^{-1}) so the hydroxyl group tends to get even farther from the negative region, the penetration depth of this molecule is smaller than that of H_2NNH_3^+ (Ref. 7). The effect is strongest for the H_3CNH_3^+ molecule where the ammonium group tends to interact with the potential region inside the polyether ring. However, this is sterically hindered, therefore, a three-point instead of a six-point matching is possible and the molecule does not penetrate into the ring at all.

Arenediazonium salts also form complexes with 18-crown-6⁸. In this case, host-guest interaction cannot be understood in terms of hydrogen bonds since they do not exist at all. In contrast, our electrostatic lock-and-key concept can be readily applied. Fig. 2 depicts the MEP of benzenediazonium cation around the $-\text{N}_2^+$ group and it is obvious that this positive region interacts favourably with its negative counterpart inside the host.

Hydration of β -trypsin-BPTI complex :

We analysed the distribution and binding energy of bound water molecules which are located by X-ray diffraction in the contact region of the β -trypsin-BPTI complex. MEP values, as calculated by our PROT POT program¹¹ at water (oxygen) positions taken from Protein Data Bank¹²⁻¹⁴ are given in Table 1. It is seen that the smallest field is 3.9 V/nm (for W413) which corresponds to a binding

Fig. 2. MEP around the $-\text{N}_2^+$ group in benzenediazonium cation. Entries are in kJ mol^{-1} .

TABLE 1—MEF VALUES (IN V/nm) FOR BOUND WATER MOLECULES (OXYGEN ATOMS) AS LOCATED BY X-RAY DIFFRACTION AROUND THE β -TRYPSIN-BPTI COMPLEX AND ITS COMPONENTS. NEIGHBOURING RESIDUES WITHIN A DISTANCE OF 400 pm (BY ITALICS FOR BPTI) ARE ALSO INDICATED

Complex		β -Trypsin		BPTI	
Water (residue) ^a	Field	Water (residue) ^b	Field	Water (residue) ^c	Field
414 (<i>Asp-189, Gly-219, Lys-15</i>)	25.1	414 (<i>Asp-189, Gly-219</i>)	17.5	—	21.6 ^d
402 (<i>Asp-189</i>)	18.6	704, 705 (<i>Asp-189</i>)	19.7	—	1.6 ^e
416 (<i>Ser-190, Lys-15</i>)	15.4	416 (<i>Ser-190</i>)	8.2	—	19.9 ^d
415 (<i>Asp-189, Ser-217, Ala-221</i>)	12.5	415 (<i>Asp-189, Ser-217, Ala-221</i>)	14.9	—	3.7 ^e
400 (<i>Cys-14</i>)	9.8	—	3.0 ^e	156 (<i>Cys-14</i>)	12.1
445 (<i>Asp-189</i>)	9.3	562 (<i>Asp-189</i>)	11.5	—	2.6 ^e
495 (<i>Trp-141, Arg-17</i>)	7.9	—	8.5 ^f	—	2.1 ^e
607 (<i>Trp-141, Arg-17</i>)	6.6	—	7.3 ^f	—	3.4 ^e
403 (<i>Gln-192, Gly-216, Pro-13</i>)	6.4	—	8.3 ^f	145 (<i>Pro-13</i>)	6.9
503 (<i>Pro-13</i>)	5.9	—	1.7 ^e	145 (<i>Pro-13</i>)	5.1
413 (<i>Arg-17</i>)	3.9	—	2.3 ^e	—	4.1 ^d

^a Ref. 12. ^b Ref. 13. ^c Ref. 14. ^d Fluctuating side chain. ^e Small field. ^f Outlier.

energy of 15 kJ mol⁻¹ (3.6 kcal mol⁻¹) in reasonable agreement with experimental and theoretical estimates¹⁵. We calculated the binding energy representing the water molecule by a point dipole having a moment of 6.47 aC.p.m (1.94 D). Most water molecules are bound quite strongly, the largest field being 25.1 V/nm (for W414) which corresponds to a binding energy of 96 kJ mol⁻¹.

Table 1 gives contributions of β -trypsin and BPTI to the field of the complex. It is an interesting feature that in practically all cases (except for W414 and W503), the resulting fields are smaller than their components originating from β -trypsin and BPTI. This means that complexation reduces the field in the contact region. This is an effect which is due to a partial complementarity between the two proteins. In the third and fifth column of Table 1 we indicated those water molecules which are bound to free β -trypsin and BPTI, respectively. Though it is clear that considerable conformational changes take place upon complexation¹⁶, therefore, the fields of β -trypsin and BPTI in the complex may considerably differ from those in the free components; it is not without interest to analyse to which extent strongly bound water molecules around these latter remain conserved in the complex.

It is clear from Table 1 that if the field calculated for a water molecule in the contact region and originating from one of the components in the complex is larger than 3.9 V/nm, the free protein also binds a water molecule. Outliers are W495, W607 and W403 for β -trypsin, and W414, W416 and W413 for BPTI. For these water molecules, the fields are large but they cannot be seen by X-ray crystallography around the free components. There is a

clear explanation for this phenomenon in case of BPTI where outlying water molecules are bound either to Lys-15 (W414 and W416) or to Arg-17 (W413). It is known that these side chains fluctuate considerably around their equilibrium positions. The root-mean-square positional fluctuations for Lys-15 and Arg-17 are 145 pm and 135 pm, respectively¹⁷. Thus, if one or more water molecules are strongly bound to one of these side chains they cannot be located by X-ray diffraction because the corresponding electronic densities are smeared. For β -trypsin, W495 and W607 are located near the protein backbone in the Trp-141 region. We do not have r.m.s. positional fluctuation values for β -trypsin, therefore, we cannot decide whether it is the strong fluctuation which makes our predictions invalid or there are other important factors not considered in the present study.

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